

Strategies for Counselling Against Teenage Pregnancy Among Female Secondary School Students in Anambra

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Abstract

The study examined the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Anambra State. The study adopted a survey research design and was guided by one research question. A total of 119 guidance counsellors were used for the study. The whole population served as the sample size. Data were collected using structured questionnaire developed by the researchers; the data were analysed using arithmetic mean. The findings showed that use of dialogue, encouraging abstinence; organizing seminars on the dangers of teenage pregnancy, among others are among the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy. Based on the findings, recommendations were made among which are; that sex education should be incorporated into the curriculum of secondary schools and guidance counsellors should initiate intensive campaign on sex education.

Key words: *Strategies, Counselling, Teenage, Pregnancy, Teenage pregnancy*

Introduction

The environment in which young people grow and make decisions related to reproductive and sexual health is becoming more challenging than ever before. This is so for many obvious reasons. Today's adolescents are being bombarded with erotic stimuli and messages through movies, music, novels and magazines. Adolescents from their earliest years watch television shows and movies that insist that sex appeal is a personal quality that people need to develop to the fullest. Ngwu (2012) opined that TV movies and music are not the only influence; the internet also provides the adolescents with seemingly unlimited access to information on sex as well as steady supply of people willing to talk about sex with them.

In other words secondary school students' sexual activities are on the increase with a trend towards earlier exposure. According to Kaestle, Morisky, and Wiley (2002), young adolescent females with substantially older partners are much more likely than their peers to have sex with

their partner, which exposes them to the risks of pregnancy and sexually transmitted diseases. Ihejiamaizu and Etuk (2010), regarding the attitude of secondary school students toward teenage pregnancy, opined that teenagers begin menstruation at early age, this early age of menarche results in early intercourse that most female students have had intercourse and most have had their first intercourse at early age. They went on to assert that peer group influence determines secondary school students' attitude towards sexual behaviour and teenage pregnancy. However, Dangal (2006) observed that most secondary school students do not approve of teenage parenthood, thus, most teenagers believe teenage pregnancy is wrong. Many believe that teenagers should not engage in sexual activity before marriage. It is culturally inappropriate for a girl to have children outside marriage despite the high value placed on pregnancy and childbirth.

On the contrary, Ogbah (2006) stated that in some cultures, teenage pregnancy among secondary school students' is accepted. In other words, the attitude of secondary school students' towards teenage pregnancy in such cultures is positive. This is because it is encouraged as a result of early marriage, for instance in the Northern Nigeria. This view is in line with Effah (2001) earlier assertion that teenage pregnancy is a welcome development in the northern part of Nigeria but not outside marriage. Some other cultures do not frown at unmarried girls getting pregnant. Durojaiye (2002) observed that in most African homes, parents are not fully equipped to answer questions on sexual matters usefully. Even those who try, pass on faulty information to their children. The whole subject thus becomes surrounded by secrecy and children now become too embarrassed to discuss this matter with their parents. Three decades after, the situation is hardly different as studies have shown that children (secondary school students inclusive) rarely receive information on sexual matters from their parents (Okonkwo & Eze, 2000). This situation leaves the secondary school students curious and ill prepared to contend with their blossoming interest in sexuality, sex and teenage pregnancy and leads them to seek information from their peers. Consequently, parent-child discussion on sexual matters is be-clouded by parental inhibitions and intergenerational tensions.

Most Nigerian parents shy away from such discussion on sex, pregnancy and its related matters, because it is generally believed that it will make the adolescent or student attempt to experiment on what they have been told. Ogbah (2006) stated that more than 50% of girls in Nigeria are sexually active or have had sexual relationship at least once. Most pregnancies among secondary school students' are unwanted because, majority of them are unmarried with no financial and physical power or strength to assume such responsibilities. Most of the pregnancies were unwanted and are terminated through unsafe abortion which is injurious to the female victim's health (Abalkhail, 1995). Nigeria culture no longer has a grip on the secondary school students as our society seems to be plagued with decayed moral codes and values and so the sense of right and wrong is eroded. This seems to affect secondary school students towards teenage pregnancy as this is manifested in the acceptance of sex before marriage and indecent dressing (Eruesegbefe, 2005).

Teenage pregnancy no doubt has far-reaching consequences on the students, family and the society. Thus, the problems that go along with teenage pregnancy extend to not only the

individual but to the society as a whole. Cases of teenage pregnancy are on the increase in Nigeria. Literature revealed that about one-half of unmarried adolescents or teenagers in Nigeria have been pregnant (Chike, 2001).

Teenage pregnancy according to Okere & Onyechi (2001) is a condition whereby a young girl of between the ages of 11 and 16 becomes pregnant when she is not yet married. Albert, Chein & Stenberg (2013) referred to teenage pregnancy as pregnancy that occurs at an early age. Magino (2008) opined that teenage pregnancy is a pregnancy by a teenager. He further, stated that teenage pregnancy is usually understood to occur in a teenage that has not completed her core education, has few or no marketable skills, is financially dependent upon her parents and/or continues to live at home and is often mentally immature. Therefore, teenage pregnancy can be referred as a parent or older sister who becomes pregnant or gives birth as a teen (13-19 years). In other words, teenage pregnancy is that which occurs at 18 years and below.

There are lots of factors responsible for teenage pregnancy. Some girls engage in sexual activities for material gains. This is usually as a result of inability of parents to meet their needs due to lack of money. Some parents do not live to their obligations to their children. There is no gain saying that some students may even get pregnant as a device to punish their parents and bring shame to the family (Okere, Anyabunam & Onyechi, 2004). Some of these teenagers help their parents and siblings with finance generated from this unwholesome activity. Some also hawk wares and this exposes them to sexual abuse or rape which could result in pregnancy. The present general economic depression according to Ogunjimi (1997) has forced so many teenagers into trading their bodies for money (commercial sex workers). This according to him is being done to either supplement their meagre financial resources or as a survival strategy.

More so, most teenagers, in an attempt to want to be like their mates in areas such as dressing, hair-do and other material things get a lot of wrong information about sex activity. Some teenagers are deceived by their peers to engage in sexual intercourse and get its taste. In some cases, they are being urged into doing that by their peers or friends who often ask them to accompany them on an errand where illicit sexual activity are carried out (Okere & Onyechi, 2001). Albert, Chein & Steinberg (2013) reported that most girls who are not involved in love relationship are usually influenced by their peers into this act. Eruesegbefe (2005) stated that education about responsible sexual behaviour and specific clear information about the danger of sexual intercourse and teenage pregnancy are frequently not offered. Thus, much of the sex education that teenagers receive and information about sex are through uninformed peers. Richter and Mlambo (2005) asserted that teenage pregnancy appears to be encouraged by lack of access to sex education. Also, the unfriendly and uncaring dispositions of nurses and those in the medical institutions who are met to provide care, create additional horror and hurdles to the teenage mothers.

Again, there is the issue of lack of sex and sexuality education in several countries especially in Nigeria. Most parents in Nigeria due to cultural and traditional norms find it difficult to engage or involve their children who are of adolescent age in sex and sexuality education. These cultural and traditional norms are so strong that the children may not be able to know the proper names of their sex or reproductive organs. This lack of proper knowledge is due

to cultural inhibitions whereby the parents use the word “pepe” to refer to male and female sex organs. Often times, the knowledge of the children about the utility of their sex organs is limited to urination. This assertion is graphically captured by Kohler, Manhart and Laffety (2008) when they opined that A global coverage measure related to sexuality education estimates that only 36% of young men and 24% of young women aged 15 – 24 years in low and middle income countries have comprehensive and correct knowledge of how to prevent pregnancy.

In certain situations, adolescent girls may not be able to resist or refuse sex. This is due to the widespread of sexual violence, and this mostly affects adolescent girls in Nigeria. There have been cases of rape which is becoming very rampant. This is further compounded by the involvement of some fathers and advanced adults in the inducement of adolescent girls in sexual coercion. Moreover, sexual coercion implies the act of forcing or attempting to force another individual- through violence, threats, verbal insistence and deception to carry out any sexual activity against the person's will (Okonofua, 2001). Sexual coercion is a continuum of behaviours ranging from unwanted touch, verbal intimidation, or any device that requires girls to sexually service men against their will. Much sexual intercourse that occurred through coercion or force can actually lead to pregnancy.

Becoming a parent, at any given age have the capacity of generating a life altering experience. Irrespective of race, education and socio-economic status, motherhood and fatherhood both place high demands on one’s life. The role of parenting comes with several responsibilities, and when teenagers become parents, the new responsibilities can be very overwhelming and daunting. Often times, teenage parents lack the support of their own parents and this can be more challenging and horrifying. Hence, such teenagers crave and seek support in adult –oriented systems in which even the older parents may find rather difficult to cope. Often times, these students drop out of school owing to pressures such as stigmatization that is linked to early parenting; isolation from their peers; and lack of the necessary support from their family, friends, schools, social service agencies and other organizations. These pressures emerge because of the cultural and normative values that teenage pregnancy tends to breach. According to Onyechi and Obikezie there are incidences and prevalence of students’ involvement in abnormal sexual behaviours. According to Attah (2010) teenage pregnancies have become a public health issue due to the observed negative impacts on prenatal outcomes and long term morbidity. Unprotected sexual intercourse can lead to an unwanted adolescent pregnancy which is often considered a serious social and public health problem. Teenagers are exposed to the high risk of unintended pregnancy (Musa, Assefa, Weldegebeal, Mitiku & Teklemariam 2016).

According to Morake (2011), schoolgirl pregnancies have doubled in the past year, despite a decade of spending on sex education and Human Immune deficiency Virus (HIV) and acquired immured deficiency syndrome (AIDS) awareness. Premature sexual intercourse results in high rates of sexually transmitted diseases, HIV transmission, adolescent pregnancy and abortions (Onyema 2006).

In reality, there are those whose health and well-being and those of their children have grown worse due to unintended pregnancy. Similarly, there would be some, though they might be few in number but who have survived the phenomenon of unintended pregnancy. Against

this background, the researchers investigate the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Anambra State.

Counselling is not just an act of advising or guiding another person, which is a common function performed by parents, teachers, and others in the society. The main task of counselling is to give the individual an opportunity to define, explore, discover and adopt ways of living a more satisfying and resourceful life within the educational, vocational environment and the society at large.

Anagbogu (2005), referred to counselling as the process of helping an individual to understand himself and his world. Therefore, counselling does not just deal with problems, problematic situation, and troubled individual but rather, it sharpens the individual understanding of themselves and their environment. Counselling is crucial in minimizing teenage pregnancy and proper counselling requires counselling strategies to tackle the problem. Ifelunni (2013), referred to counselling strategies as the theories, techniques and skills needed by a counsellor to achieve a certain goal and objective. To go through the process of assisting clients to modify their behaviour, counsellors need tools; such tools are called skills and techniques and are gotten from theories.

Strategies to be used in counselling against teenage pregnancy include: cognitive restructuring, self-control, problem solving skill, dialogue, modelling, self-directive behaviour, encouraging abstinence, sex education, shaping, laying out the consequences, verbal communication techniques, among others (Mcintosh, Pruet & Kelly (2014). There are so many counselling strategies and techniques to be used to counselling against teenage pregnancy. These strategies and techniques are gotten from cognitive, affective and behaviour theories, (Coleman, Wheeler and Webber 1993). It is against these backdrops that the researchers were motivated to carry out this research on Strategies used in counselling against teenage pregnancy among adolescents female secondary school students.

Statement of the Problem

Counselling as a profession is geared towards proffering solutions on issues that hamper on the general wellbeing of humanity. In achieving this function the counsellors adopt some strategies. The strategies adopted are determined by the nature of the behavioural problem. Pregnancy is a normal phenomenon but its acceptance revolves around the time frame, the circumstance and who is involved. Thus, when pregnancy occurs among unmarried female adolescents it is referred as teenage pregnancy.

Adolescents are the leaders of tomorrow and so they require proper guidance that will propel them into responsible productive adults useful to themselves and their nations. In a situation whereby they are not properly guided or directed, many in the bid to experiment or discover, fall victim of unwanted pregnancy. Teenage Pregnancy also brings about over population, leads to unemployment which leads to increased crime wave and a number of other social vices (Ikwuako, 2001).

The issue of teenage pregnancy in our contemporary society has been considered an epidemic and endemic in nature, which constitutes social problem that should require social

action for solution. Because, the rate of youngsters especially females dropping out of schools have been on the increase. Having observed political, socio-economic and socio-cultural effects of teenage pregnancy, it becomes pertinent for individuals, parents, teachers, mosque, non-governmental organization groups and churches to intervene. Psychological effects of Teenage pregnancy ranges from fear of the unknown, compromised marriage prospects, emotional stress among others. It has been observed that most teenagers especially the unmarried pregnant ones express, self doubt, loneliness, uncertainty and helplessness than their peers.

The researchers have observed and even reviewed literature that hamper on the incidences of teenagers putting to bed and dumping them inside the gutters or waste bins. This has posed a very big challenge to adolescents, parents, teachers, counsellors and the society at large. Adolescent stage being a period of discovery, as such most adolescents lack adequate information on how to take care of their body and the baby, and they end up becoming uneducated and liability to the society at large. It is no doubt that teenage pregnancy is a social malady eating deep in our entire society. Thus, the need to explore the counselling strategies is undisputable. It is against this background that the researchers seek to determine the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female students in Anambra State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Anambra State. Specifically, the study determined the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Anambra State.

Research Question

What are the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Anambra State?

METHOD

Research Design

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The descriptive survey research design according to Akpunonu (2007), is one in which a group of people or item is studied by collecting and analysing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group.

The study was carried out in Anambra State. Anambra State is one of the thirty-six states of Nigeria. It is located in the South-Eastern part of the country. The state is bounded in the East by Enugu State, in the West by Delta State, in the North by Kogi State and in South by Abia and Imo States. The counsellors in the public secondary schools were used for the study. The people in the area under study comprise of traders, farmers, artisans, civil and public servants. The major languages of the people are Igbo and English.

The population of the study comprised of 119 counsellors from public secondary schools in Anambra State. (School Records, PPSSC: Awka 2016). Since the population of the study is

small, all the 119 school counsellors were used in carrying out the study. Hence, there was no sampling.

The instrument used for data collection is a structured questionnaire on the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Anambra State. The questionnaire is designed to elicit and extract vital information from the respondents. A four scale format was used namely; strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD).

A face to face administration was used by the researchers, whereby the researchers visited the counsellors during their monthly counsellors' association meeting and administered the questionnaires to the respondents; a total number of 110 questionnaires were administered. The questionnaire was collected from the respondents by the researchers on the spot in order to avoid loss. In the long run, 110 questionnaires were completed, collected and used for data analysis. The Data collected in this study were analysed using mean. The critical point was calculated as follows the mid-mean value is 2.5, the decision rule, therefore, is that any of the response item for which the mean score is 2.5 and above was taken to mean that the respondents agreed, while any response item for which the mean score is below 2.5 was taken as disagreed.

The questionnaire has twenty item statements.

S/N	Item	Mean X	Decision
1	Use Dialogue.	3.05	positive
2	Encouraging abstinence.	3.33	positive
3	Encouraging verbal communication skill	3.38	positive
4	Organizing seminars on the dangers of teenage pregnancy/ sex talk.	3.72	positive
5	Implementing sex education in the school curriculum.	2.88	positive
6	Flogging/physical punishment	1.72	Negative
7	Use of Assertive training	2.16	Negative
8	Application of Time out.	2.11	Negative
9	Encouraging the use of contraceptive.	2.22	Negative
10	Use of Role playing.	3.05	Positive
11	Cognitive restructuring.	3.5	Positive
12	Expulsion from school.	1.72	Negative
13	Use of Self –control strategies	3.66	Positive
14	Use of Manual labour.	1.6	Negative
15	Application of Aversion strategies	2.27	Negative
16	Use of Ear-shooting strategies	2.38	Negative
17	Use of Stimulus control	2.44	Negative

18	Application of Shaping steps	3.11	Positive
19	Laying out the consequences	3.27	Positive
20	Use of proximity control	2.92	Positive

This table shows that respondents agreed that; dialogue (3.05), encouraging abstinence (3.33), encouraging verbal communication skill (3.38), organizing seminars on the dangers of teenage pregnancy/ sex talk (3.72), role-playing (3.05), cognitive restructuring (3.5), self-control (3.66), shaping (3.11), laying out the consequences (4.77), proximity control (2.55) and implementing sex education in school curriculum (2.88), , are the strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students and rejects flogging (1.72), assertiveness training (2.16), Time-out (2.11), encouraging the use of contraceptives (2.22), expulsion from school (1.72), manual labour (1.61), aversion (2.27), ear shooting (2.38), and stimulus control (2.44).

Discussion of Findings

The major findings of the study are briefly discussed as follows:

The strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students are dialogue, encouraging abstinence, encouraging verbal communication skill, organizing seminars on the dangers of teenage pregnancy. Also sex talk, role-playing, cognitive restructuring, self-control, lay out the consequences, proximity control and implementing sex education in school curriculum.

From the findings it is observed that counsellors commonly employ such strategies like; Encouraging Abstinence, Dialogue, Cognitive Restructuring, self Control, Shaping, laying out the Consequences, Role-Playing , Organizing seminars on the dangers of teenage pregnancy among others, in counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students. According to Adler, Catherine & West (2014) decision making programs may be provided by the school and the curriculum is based on the value or mission of the school; for example, abstinence only. However, the school counsellor must adapt and modify the curriculum based on the students and their needs while adhering to the distinct policies. Helping students to understand themselves sexually and to become comfortable with the idea of romantic relationships is crucial to the development of adolescent romantic relationships in the future. Another emphasis is placed on the importance of "connectedness" and honesty and trust when talking about sex education. When adolescents feel that they can trust an adult or advocate, or health education teacher, they know that their feelings are being considered and understood.

Depending on the school's policy for sex education, school counsellors may have to follow that particular curriculum. Health educators, science teachers and family studies educators can all be partners in the process. Just as lessons are modified, for different learning styles, school counsellors need to modify sex education information to the level of maturity, development and understanding for adolescents. Sex education would begin with a theory of sexuality expansive

enough to include experiences such as curiosity, infatuation, attraction, making friends, narcissism, losing oneself to love, becoming mad with desire, feeling unwanted, rejection, hating your parents, and being disappointed (Gilbert, 2007).

Implications of the Study:

Teenagers who are pregnant face many difficult issues and counselling can be an important source of help. The procedure for counselling should begin with a review of the scope and consequences of teenage pregnancy. The society in the bid to retain its worth and preserve its citizens, the adolescents among other issues must be made to recognize the implications and consequences of teenage pregnancy. Given the fact that teenage pregnancy blows neither the adolescents nor the society at large any good breeze, it is only reasonable to fight against it with full force.

Counselling strategies should therefore be aimed at building rapport with techniques such as maintaining confidentiality, avoiding judgemental steering and gearing communication to cognitive maturity. Hence counsellors who are able to discuss such strategies can help teenage pregnancy adolescents make informed decisions and their future prospects improve.

Recommendations

Consequent to the findings of this study, the researchers made the following recommendations:

1. The curriculum committee should introduce sex education as a compulsory subject area in secondary school curriculum.
2. The school counsellors should enforce prevention strategies by encouraging abstinence rather than intervention.
3. Guidance counsellors should occasionally use different strategies to inculcate in the secondary school students relevant knowledge about dangers of teenage pregnancy and its consequences.
4. Finally the researchers advocate government to organize public enlightenment campaign every year on the role of adolescents, guidance counsellors, teachers and parents in minimizing teenage pregnancy.

Conclusion

This work x-rayed strategies for counselling against teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Anambra state. Some revealed that adolescents have little or no knowledge on the dangers and consequences of teenage pregnancy. Thus, the following conclusions were reached.

Teenage pregnancy is at its peak among adolescents due to ignorance of its dangers and effects. This high incidence of teenage pregnancy can be attributed to wrong orientation and misconception.

Adults are not comfortable discussing sex education with adolescents even when adults feel like discussing it, adolescents on their own are always too secretive and prefer keeping sex issues to themselves.

Sex education is not taught in secondary schools and guidance counsellors don't make effort to teach students sex education.

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